

A VISCOMETRIC METHOD FOR STUDYING THE KINETICS OF ALCOHOLYSIS OF ESTERS

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Using a modification of Scarpa's method, satisfactory values for the unimolecular constants are obtained for the alcoholysis of methyl acetate by three alcohols in the presence of hydrochloric acid at 25° and 30°, by following the progress of the change by a determination of the viscosity of the medium. It is considered that the procedure can be of general use for a study of the kinetics of changes in liquid media.

Kinetics of alcoholysis have been studied *polarimetrically* by Patterson and Dickinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 280), Bruni and Contardi (*Gazzetta*, 1906, 36, 356) and Dasannacharya (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1924, 7, 1; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1627); *dilatometrically* by Anderson and Holden (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, 18, 152), Kolhatker (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1915, 1, 107) and Dasannacharya (*ibid.*, 1921, 4, 181); *conductometrically* by Nixon and Branch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 492, 2499). Following the work of Joshi and Raju (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.* 1932, *Chem. Section*, p. 193) and Joshi and Joga Rao (*ibid.*, 1933, p. 190) the kinetics of the above reaction were investigated *viscometrically*. It will be seen from a consideration of the experimental procedure detailed below that this method possesses some marked advantages over those in use hitherto, in the wider range of its applicability and the comparative simplicity of the necessary apparatus.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general experimental arrangement was already described in detail by Joshi and Vishwanathan (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 330) which is Scarpa's method (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271; Farrow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101,347). The chief advantage here is that unlike in the case of the familiar Ostwald's method, no density measurements are required; t_1 , the time of rise of a certain constant volume of the reaction mixture under a known suction, and t_2 , the time of fall for the same quantity of the liquid under its own hydrostatic pressure, being all that are needed. For accuracy of measurement, constancy of the suction pressure is essential; in the present experiments it was 30 ± 0.03 cm. of water. From a knowledge of t_1 and t_2 , the viscosity, η , is given by

$$\eta = k.t_1.t_2/(t_1 + t_2)$$

where k is a constant for a given viscometer and applied suction and t_1 and t_2 , the times taken for the rise and fall of the liquid in the viscometer. k was evaluated from observations of t_1 and t_2 at a known temperature for a standard liquid like water for which viscosity, η , is known. Two Scarpa tubes were connected suitably to the aspirator, which enabled the progress of two reactions to be followed simultaneously. The values of k , the viscometric constants for the two Scarpa tubes used, are 0'5537 and 0'5869.

The volume of the reaction mixture was 30 c.c. in all the cases; it consisted of 5 c.c. of the ester, methyl acetate in the present experiments, 20 c.c. of an alcohol and 5 c.c. of the latter containing a known amount of hydrochloric acid introduced as a pure dry gas, to act as a catalyst. The various constituents of the mixture, namely the ester, the alcohol and the hydrochloric acid gas were carefully purified and freed from moisture by appropriate methods. For the actual preparation of the reaction mixture, the above amount of alcohol was kept in a tall gas jar and closed with the rubber stopper which admitted the Scarpa-tube; this and the two other liquids contained in well stoppered bottles were allowed to attain the temperature of the thermostat, then mixed in the above gas jar and the corresponding mean time noted. Measurements of viscosity of the reacting mixture were then made at stated time intervals, for a period of 4-10 hours, depending upon the rate of the particular alcoholysis reaction. The mixture was then allowed to stand for about 24 hours, when the final reading was taken. In all cases viscosity was measured at suitable intervals for another 24 hours to ascertain the constancy of the final reading mentioned above corresponding to the end-points of the reaction. In a few cases viscosity showed a slight diminution even after the first 24 hours, and the lowest reading was taken. The reactions were studied at two temperatures, 25° and 30°, the temperature of the water in the thermostat being maintained constant within $\pm 0'05^\circ$ by employing a toluene thermoregulator and a motor driven stirrer. The unimolecular velocity constants were obtained by employing the equation,

$$k = \frac{2303}{t} \cdot \log_{10} \frac{a}{(a-x)}$$

The concentration of the unchanged ester at a time t was obtained on the assumption that $(a-x)$ was proportional to $(\eta_t - \eta_\infty)$. Straight lines were obtained by plotting $\log(a-x)$ against t , in all the reactions studied. $\log a$ was then obtained from each of these lines by extrapolation to zero time. Curve B is one of such typical plot for the reaction corresponding to Table VI and curve A is another plot for the same reaction illustrating the nature of the viscosity variation of the system with time during alcoholysis (Fig. 1).

In all the experiments methyl acetate was the ester employed. Hydrochloric acid present in different concentrations served as the catalyst. Amyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-propyl alcohols were used for replacing the alkyl group in the ester. Typical experimental results obtained are shown in the following tables for the different reactions.

TABLE I.

Conc. of catalyst = 0.1830*N*-HCl. Temp. = 30 ± 0.05°. *k* = 0.5537.
Methyl acetate + amyl alcohol + catalyst = 5, 20, 5 c.c. respectively.

<i>t</i> ₁ .	<i>t</i> ₂ .	<i>η</i> .	(<i>a</i> - <i>x</i>).	log (<i>a</i> - <i>x</i>).	<i>t</i> (min.)	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ .
				log <i>a</i> = 1.1770	0' by extrapolation.	
6' 18.6"	7' 0.3"	1.855	0.140	.1461	17.0	(4.15)
6 16.3	7 6.4	1.843	0.130	.1139	35.0	(4.15)
6 15.0	7 3.8	1.835	0.120	.0792	55.0	4.10
6 12.6	7 1.2	1.824	0.109	.0374	80.0	4.03
6 9.7	6 58.4	1.810	0.095	.29777	120.5	3.85
6 6.8	6 57.3	1.801	0.086	.9395	139.0	4.03
6 5.9	6 56.5	1.797	0.082	.9138	153.0	3.96
6 3.7	6 53.6	1.785	0.070	.8451	189.0	4.05
6 2.1	6 52.2	1.779	0.064	.8062	227.5	3.75
5 59.7	6 50.0	1.768	0.053	.7243	263.0	3.96
5 59.3	6 48.8	1.764	0.049	.6902	282.0	3.98
5 57.5	6 47.4	1.758	0.043	.6335	320.0	3.91
5 55.3	6 45.0	1.746	0.031	.4914	412.0	3.82
5 53.7	6 42.4	1.736	0.021	.3222	527.0	3.73
5 49.3	6 37.5	1.175	0		∞	
						Mean 3.93

TABLE II.

Conc. of catalyst = 0.1830*N*-HCl. Temp. = 25 ± 0.05°. *k* = 0.5870.
Methyl acetate + amyl alcohol + catalyst = 5, 20, 5 c.c. respectively

<i>t</i> ₁ .	<i>t</i> ₂ .	<i>η</i> .	(<i>a</i> - <i>x</i>).	Log (<i>a</i> - <i>x</i>).	<i>t</i> (min.)	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ .
				log <i>a</i> = 1.2200	0' by extrapolation.	
6' 17.5"	7' 30.0"	2.008	0.146	.1644	24.0	(5.24)
6 16.6	7 28.0	2.002	0.140	.1461	54.0	(3.16)
6 17.0	7 26.5	2.000	0.138	.1399	71.0	2.60
6 13.5	7 25.0	1.985	0.123	.0899	108.5	2.74
6 13.4	7 23.0	1.983	0.121	.0823	125.0	2.53
6 10.3	7 20.4	1.969	0.106	.0253	167.5	2.67
6 10.2	7 19.6	1.966	0.104	.0170	189.0	2.46
6 7.0	7 17.4	1.952	0.090	.29542	234.0	2.62
6 5.0	7 14.5	1.940	0.078	.8921	285.0	2.65
6 3.6	7 13.7	1.935	0.073	.8633	316.5	2.60
6 1.6	7 12.2	1.926	0.064	.8092	356.0	2.67
6 1.0	7 11.0	1.992	0.060	.7782	387.5	2.63
5 50.6	6 56.8	1.862	0.0		∞	
						Mean 2.62

TABLE V.

Conc. of catalyst = 0.1483*N*-HCl. Temp. = 30 ± 0.05°. $k = 0.5870$.
 Methyl acetate + *isobutyl* alcohol + catalyst = 5, 20, 5 c.c. respectively.

t_1 .	t_2 .	η .	$(a-x)$.	$\log(a-x)$.	t (min.).	$k \times 10^3$.
				$\log a = \bar{1}.1325$	0	
5' 33.2"	6' 25.0"	1.748	0.133	.1239	14.5	1.36
5' 31.6	6' 24.3	1.742	0.127	.1038	29.0	(2.28)
5' 28.5	6' 21.6	1.727	0.112	.0492	74.5	2.58
5' 27.0	6' 19.8	1.718	0.103	.0128	122.5	(2.26)
5' 24.6	6' 17.1	1.706	0.091	.29590	151.5	2.65
5' 23.6	6' 15.6	1.700	0.085	.9294	175.0	2.67
5' 22.2	6' 13.5	1.691	0.076	.8808	221.5	2.63
5' 20.6	6' 11.8	1.684	0.069	.8388	283.5	2.39
5' 19.0	6' 10.0	1.676	0.061	.7853	320.0	2.51
5' 17.4	6' 9.5	1.670	0.055	.7404	347.5	2.60
5' 15.0	6' 7.8	1.661	0.046	.6628	387.0	2.79
5' 15.0	6' 6.8	1.658	0.043	.6335	423.5	2.72
5' 14.3	6' 5.8	1.654	0.039	.5911	466.5	2.67
5' 12.8	6' 4.6	1.647	0.032	.5051	510.0	2.83
5' 11.2	6' 3.6	1.641	0.026	.4150	609.0	2.72
4' 7.9	5' 57.5	1.615	0		=	
					Mean	2.65

TABLE VI.

Conc. of catalyst = 0.1483*N*-HCl. Temp. = 25 ± 0.05°. $k = 0.5537$.
 Methyl acetate + *isobutyl* alcohol + catalyst = 5, 20, 5 c.c. respectively.

t_1 .	t_2 .	η .	$(a-x)$.	$\log(a-x)$.	t (min.).	$k \times 10^3$.
				$\log a = \bar{1}.1265$		
4' 40.6"	7' 50.2"	1.823	0.136	.1335	12.0	
5' 39.0	7' 49.0	1.816	0.129	.1106	27.0	1.36
5' 38.4	7' 48.2	1.813	0.126	.1004	45.0	1.34
5' 37.8	7' 46.8	1.808	0.121	.0828	75.0	1.34
5' 36.0	7' 46.0	1.801	0.114	.0569	120.0	1.34
5' 35.0	7' 44.6	1.796	0.109	.0374	153.0	1.34
5' 34.0	7' 42.4	1.789	0.102	.0086	204.4	1.33
5' 33.0	7' 41.0	1.783	0.096	.29820	250.0	1.33
15.4	7' 14.8	1.687	0		=	
					Mean	1.34

TABLE VII.

Conc. of catalyst = 0.2N-HCl. Temp. = 30 ± 0.05. $k = 0.5537$
 Methyl acetate + *n*-propyl alcohol + *n*-catalyst = 5, 20, 5 c.c. respectively.

t_1	t_2	t	$(a-x)$	$\log(a-x)$	(min.)	$k \times 10^3$		
				$\log a = 2.8200$	0			
4'	59.2"	6'	48.6"	1.593	0.061	72.53	21.0	3.30
4	56.5	6	46.6	1.582	0.050	69.90	30.0	3.48
4	56.0	6	45.2	1.578	0.046	68.27	109.5	3.52
4	54.7	6	44.0	1.572	0.040	66.21	144.5	3.48
4	53.2	6	42.9	1.565	0.033	65.185	195.5	3.35
4	53.0	8	41.6	1.563	0.031	64.914	220.0	3.45
4	51.4	6	41.4	1.557	0.025	64.79	241.5	4.03
4	51.2	6	41.3	1.557	0.025	64.79	255.5	3.80
4	50.6	6	38.4	1.552	0.020	64.010	303.5	3.4
4	48.6	6	37.8	1.543	0.011	64.14	340.0	(3.27)
4	48.5	6	36.5	1.541	0.009	63.9542	374.0	(3.34)
4	46.6	6	34.0	1.532	0		∞	
						Mean	3.65	

DISCUSSION

After the intermediate complex-formation theory for esterification reactions demonstrated by Goldschmidt and co-workers in a series of papers (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, 60, 728; 1912, 81, 30; 1929, 143, 139, 278), the mechanism of acid-catalysed alcoholysis reactions may be represented as comprising initially the formation of complexes of the H-ions from the catalyst with the alcohol molecules, the interchange of the alkyl group in the ester taking place subsequently by the interaction between these complexes and the ester under test. The alcoholysis of methyl acetate may therefore be represented as follows:—

Where R_x is the alkyl group which is sought to interchange with the methyl group of methyl acetate. The rate of alcoholysis may be expressed by the equation.

$$\frac{d(R_x \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5)}{dt} = k (\text{CH}_3 \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5)(R_x \text{OH}_2^+)$$

As, however, the alcohol $R_x\text{OH}$ was maintained to be present in great excess in all the reactions studied, its concentration and therefore its active mass may be taken

to remain practically constant throughout the reaction, and the equation reduces to one of the first order. The velocity constant, k , is then given by,

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{a}{a-x}$$

This is in satisfactory agreement with the experimental results as can be seen from the concordant values of k , given in the last column of the above tables.

From curve A (Fig. 1) and from the viscosity data given in column 3 in the

FIG. 1.

tables, it is clear that the variation in viscosity of the reacting mixture during the progress of alcoholysis is appreciable enough in magnitude to be easily measured by the present experimental method, and to enable the velocity constants to be computed by applying the appropriate law for the particular reaction. It is thus seen that measurement of viscosity variations with time employing a Scarpa's type of viscometer, constitutes a very simple method of studying the kinetics of alcoholysis of esters.

The effect of increasing the strength of the catalyst, keeping other things the same, is shown in Tables II, III and IV. The mean values of k , obtained therein, are seen to be directly proportional to the concentrations of the hydro-

chloric acid employed as catalyst. This is in agreement with a similar experimental finding of Kolbaker (*loc. cit.*) for the alcoholysis of isobutyl acetate in presence of methyl alcohol, catalysed by HCl acid. This is expected to be so, since in dry alcohol the concentration of alcohol-complex may be considered to be equal to the total H⁺ concentration, or in this case, where a strong mineral acid is used, to the concentration of such acid.

The influence of temperature on the reaction velocity is seen in the values of the velocity constants obtained at 25° and 30°. The values of the velocity constants are nearly doubled by 5° rise in temperature (*i.e.*) from 25° to 30°. It was intended to continue this work with a view to obtaining the velocity constants at two or three other temperatures and evaluate the activation energies.

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